

THE LANGUAGE OF BUSINESS COMMUNICATION IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS

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Annotation: A rapidly growing body of research demonstrates that linguistic diversity influences almost all managerial decisions in today's multinational corporations, economic development and human capital development. While the practical value of language is undeniable, empirical research and theoretical understanding of their complex and multifaceted effects still provide interesting material for research.

Keywords: Linguistic diversity, interdisciplinary theorizing, language of business communication, human capital

Modern international scholars consider the language of business communication as a very important tool, since the language determines organizational communication, constitutes and is considered important for building organizational realities. Emphasizing the theoretical and practical importance of language in international business communication, it must be emphasized that language permeates every facet of international business.

Language has a direct impact on management processes in the development of business communication. Language in international business is a real example of a situation where "the medium is communication", it is suspected that the language used to convey information can significantly change the intended content of the message. In the modern business world, communication takes place not only between native speakers of the same language; most often business meetings

between representatives of different countries become a form of international cooperation and the development of world trade. The linguistic features of different countries can become a barrier to such cooperation. The study of the interaction of elements of socio-economic mechanisms for increasing knowledge of languages contributes to the creation of not only a logical-functional, but also an organizational structure, meeting modern requirements and ensuring consistent and efficient implementation of priority tasks. The structure and composition of the interaction of elements of socio-economic mechanisms for ensuring knowledge of languages and economic development have been developed (Fig. 1).

Rice. 1. Interaction of elements of socio-economic mechanisms for ensuring knowledge of languages and business communication¹

Translation remains an important part of the language challenge, given the sheer volume of material that needs to be translated just for the daily smooth running of meetings and organizations. However, it is important that in the process of translating large text materials one should not lose sight of what should be paid attention to - translators today are not just translators, but also effective communicators and organizers, owners of information. In this regard, the language of business communication becomes a tool for established ties and friendly communication, as well as a field for integration interactions and economic cooperation.

The first generation of research considers language as an ethnic attribute. Mother tongue assigns a person to a particular group, and this linguistic

¹Developed by the author.

attribution can affect that person's socioeconomic status and his or her earnings. This applies, for example, to immigrants in the US versus the “white” workforce, Anglophones and Francophones in Canada, between “guest workers” and native Germans in Germany, and between three language communities in Switzerland.

Language Dynamics: The second generation of research focuses on language as a source of economic advantage. Language skills can be seen as an area in which individuals and societies can profitably invest. You will find examples of this in the studies summarized below.

Language and economic activity: The third generation of research looks at both dimensions simultaneously. Languages are seen not only as elements of identity or potentially valuable skills, but rather as a set of

Since linguists and linguists are often given access to more information, great care must be taken when dealing with a large amount of material. Language audit and translation should be part of an integrated approach to solving the language issue, including recruitment, training and placement of personnel.

Marketing research of personnel is carried out at such stages as determining the main goals, important problems and tasks, collecting and analyzing information on the main elements of the labor market conjuncture, searching for a discrepancy between supply and demand for labor, developing measures to reduce unemployment, bringing their ratio into line .

Table 2

Measures to create supply and demand for a labor force with knowledge of various languages

No.	Formation of demand for labor	Formation of labor supply
1.	Increasing the efficiency of existing	Involvement in family business and

	and creating new jobs for women	handicrafts, development of various forms of self-employment
2.	Introducing new methods of creating jobs through innovation	Put the responsibility for retraining, retraining and advanced training of personnel on the students themselves
3.	Organization of paid public works	Arrange working hours, set working hours based on interests
4.	Reducing the demand for labor in one sector and redistributing them to other sectors	Improving the regulation of the movement of female labor in the external and internal markets, as well as in the form of labor migration.

The main implication of this finding is that knowledge of foreign markets is a valuable resource that can be an important source of a country's competitive advantage. The institutional features of certain regions determine the features of economic interaction between business partners from different countries. The norms of behavior, the existing protocol, behavioral features - all this can be conveyed by those who are engaged in translation and are a link between different civilizations. In fact, knowledge about economic characteristics and about the world market gives an idea of who has what, what can be used, what opportunities are available, and with whom there is competition. Countries tend to vary greatly in terms of market dynamics, competitive environment, institutional environment, language and culture. In research, conducted by various agencies to study the impact of language proficiency on the level of business activity and economic development, the hypothesis was confirmed that knowledge of foreign markets positively affects the success of a company in international markets. Although managerial linguistic skills are considered to be key to international business success, and this is especially true for foreign companies doing business in non-

English speaking countries, such as Kazakh or Russian, cannot by themselves be the main reason for success. Another possible reason may be the presence of demand for the production of foreign products in the country due to the lack of production and the conditions associated with the transition economy. Moreover, foreign companies may rely primarily on informal relationships and networks with which they have a common language.

Language plays a modest role in economic analysis, reflecting the dual notions that economic processes, being fundamental, transcend language and culture, and therefore do not have a significant impact on economic variables. However, since the mid-1960s, a specialization called "economics of language" has appeared precisely in order to study the impact of language knowledge on the economic development of countries. In fact, knowledge of the language, knowledge of the intricacies of business communication and institutional development features allow us to draw conclusions about the impact of the level of knowledge on the economic activity of society as a whole and the economy as one of the components of well-being.

There are statistics that the part of the population that knows more than two languages, on average, save 31% more per year and save 39% more by retirement. Moreover, native speakers pay more attention to their health: they are 24% less likely to smoke, 29% more likely to exercise and 31% less likely to be obese.²

²<https://econs.online/en/articles/economics/the-economics-of-language/>

Rice. 3. Comparison of the actual level of employment with theoretical data³

The position of people with knowledge of two or more languages in the labor market is determined not only by changes in their composition, level and main indicators, but also by the territorial location of labor resources. We propose an economic and mathematical model that will provide a methodical implementation of the proposed integrated program approach (Fig. 3).

In our opinion, in order to develop targeted programs to promote employment at the state level, aimed at increasing the desire to find a job among people with knowledge of the language, stimulating their abilities and capabilities, eliminating the barriers that exist, it is necessary to identify groups of the unemployed, apply specific socio-economic mechanisms to increase their employment. .

The strategy of this model is characterized by the fact that it is aimed at the full implementation of the methodology for determining the optimal parameters of the labor market and unemployment by calculating, in the context of areas, the unemployed population in need of employment using the existing employment

³Mwallif tomonidan ishlab chikilgan.

system.

Since ancient times, trade has been the main economic incentive for language learning. In the modern world, the closer the languages of two countries, the greater their bilateral trade, and, on average, a common language (native or official) increases trade flows by almost 50%. In turn, an increase in trade volume increases the number of people willing to learn a trading partner's language: on average, there is a 13% chance that a doubling of trade volume will lead to more language learning. The growth of Sino-English trade seems to encourage the learning of Chinese in native English-speaking countries, as well as the learning of English in China. Higher birth rates among the Arabic and Spanish speaking population will encourage more people to learn the two languages, while the population

The researchers used data on daily transactions in Finland, where the official languages are Finnish and Swedish.⁴(Swedish is spoken by about 7% of the population and 93% speak Finnish). They also defined the culture of the firm according to the name of its CEO. It turned out that native Swedish speakers invest more in firms that publish their annual reports in Swedish and are associated with Swedish culture, while Finnish-speaking investors are more likely to choose firms that share their language and culture. Companies that communicate in Swedish are about 15 times more popular with Swedish-speaking investors than companies that communicate in Finnish, and vice versa. Two Finnish companies in the sample published reports exclusively in Swedish, and both had an overwhelming majority of Swedish-speaking investors. A similar correlation between investor behavior and language differences was found in Belgium, where the two main languages are French and Dutch. French-speaking investors are more likely to buy French stocks and shares in companies from

⁴econs.online/en/articles/economics/the-economics-of-language

countries where French is a common language. Dutch speakers prefer to invest in assets related to the Netherlands.

Thus, we can conclude that language development and knowledge of the language of business communication has a direct impact on the development of society, economic development and personal development. The given examples testify to the impact on the investment climate and the development of society of the factors of the development of language cognition.

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